

Design of electric chiral magnonic resonators coupled to single mode magnonic conduits

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The original electric chiral magnonic resonator (ECMR) proposed by considering a micromagnetic model in two dimensional (2D) space is now extended into the third dimension. The new ECMR device in the three dimensional (3D) space is designed to couple to a magnonic waveguide operating in a single mode fashion. The single mode operation allows each device to be approximated as a lump element, in which its behaviour could be predicted by a lump element model (previously presented as “analytical model”). The existence of the lump element model allow fast calculation of the device behaviour without resorting to the more time and computational power consuming micromagnetic simulation, thus enable fast analysis of neural network or reservoir computing circuitry formed by combining multiple number of these ECMR devices connected through single mode magnonic waveguides.

Index Terms—magnonics, spin waves, neural network, reservoir computing.

I. INTRODUCTION

IT is believed that artificial intelligence hold the key to the next wave of technology revolution. Unfortunately, recent successful developments in artificial intelligence are largely based on conventional computer technology in form of silicon based CPU/GPU, i.e. digital representation of information by CMOS hardware built according to generally von-Neumann architecture. Such conventional computer technology, while produce tremendous success in performing conventional computational task, is highly inefficient in implementing artificial intelligence which manifest itself in form of energy consumption. Indeed, data centres in United States that support artificial intelligence are already consuming 4.4% of the country’s electricity, and is likely to double or triple in the coming years [1]. The need to lower energy consumption of artificial intelligence services become imminent. To address this challenge of our generation, numerous computation paradigms based on unconventional building material, information carrier and computational architecture have been proposed. This range from memristic electronic device [2], phase change material based photonic device [3], nano-oscillator or skyrmion based spintronics [4], [5], etc. Among these candidates, magnonics [6], a sub-field of spintronics, may not seem to be the most promising candidate at the a first glance, worth further attention due to its advantage of low level of operation energy when comparing with other alternative paradigms. While the information carrier of magnonics is spin wave, which has the feature of inherently non-linear [7] and scalable to small dimension [47], both indispensable to implement computation, the strengths of magnonics lies with the miniscule amount of energy required to excite and manipulate these spin waves [9]. This prompt magnonics to be a perfect solution to address the aforementioned artificial intelligence energy consumption problem.

Numerous efforts to utilize spin waves for a broader scope of computation/optimization (which includes neuromorphic

computation that could lead to artificial intelligence) has been attempted recently. These attempts can be subdivided into two main categories: “Magnonics-electronics hybrid design” [10]–[12], and “All magnonics design” [13]–[15]. Given that multiple intermediate steps are involved in the computational process, computational information in “Magnonics-electronics hybrid” design is being converted back and forth between electrical and spin wave signal through the multiple intermediate steps. The electric part of the signal participate actively in the computational process. So far for all attempt in this category, the electric part of the system is provided by macroscopic instrument, and on-chip electronic device that coexist with the magnonic part of the system has not been realized. On the other hand, for “all magnonics design”, the computational information is represented purely in form of spin wave signal on a monolithic substrate through the multiple computational steps. Signal is being converted from and into electric form only at the beginning and the end of the computational process. Certainly designs within this category come with the advantage of physical compactness when compared with the first category since no bulky electronic instrument is involved (other than the excitation and read out process, which does not count as the computational process itself). Even if on-chip devices that enable electrical-spin wave hybridization has been realized that satisfies the desire for miniaturization, “all magnonic design” still carries the advantage of energy efficiency over the “hybrid design” since in the “all magnonic design”, no energy wasteful back and forth conversion between electrical and spin wave signal is necessary.

Unfortunately, “all magnonic” computational system proposed until today remain largely passive [13]–[15] (not counting the electrical part that is responsible for initial excitation and final read out), i.e. no gain exist for the spin wave signal that perform the multiple intermediate calculation steps. This is because spin wave amplification remain an elusive subject until recently. To invoke amplification, the signal has to be back converted into electrical form, i.e. back to the “hybrid design”, which leads to drawback of energy

consumption aforementioned. Currently, the price to pay for to have a “all magnonic” system is for the computational process to utilize only passive component. Certainly this approach would greatly limit the functionality of the system and remains unsatisfactory. The need for direct spin wave amplification without converting the signal into electrical format become obvious. First of all, Yttrium Iron Garnet (YIG) remains the most credible choice of material to construct magnonics system due to the low damping property of YIG [16]. The usage of YIG as the magnonic medium rules out the recently theoretically proposed black hole horizon radiation like mechanism as a solution for spin wave amplification in magnonics [17], [18], as the mechanism applies only to metallic magnetic material but not YIG, which is an electrical insulator. On the other hand, there are recent successful experimental realization of spin wave amplification in YIG using Bose-Einstein Condensation [19] and spin orbit torque (SOT) pumping [20]. Magnonic repeater has been constructed using non-linear dependence of spin wave excitation efficiency in YIG by metallic microstrip transducer [21], which can also be regarded as spin wave amplification in the broader sense.

While the recent advances in obtaining gain with spin wave mentioned above are impressive, there are shortcomings with these approaches that could not be ignored. Artificial intelligences are based on neuromorphic computations, which is more natural and efficient to be represented in analog rather than digital format. In fact, this is part of the reason that a human biological brain is still much more energetically efficient than it’s silicon counterpart [22]. To construct an analog computer, ones need amplification of continuous wave (cw) signal rather than digital ones. This render the stimulated amplification mechanism [19] and the magnonic repeater [21] proposed above unsuitable for the scope as they applies only to pulse signal but not cw. Neither the SOT pumping mechanism [20] could be applied to cw signal, as the inherent unstable nature of the mechanism produce spontaneous oscillations when operating in cw mode. Given the light shed upon as above, the “electric chiral magnonic resonator” (ECMR) proposed recently in [23] and [24] worth further investigation since it is capable of providing gain to cw spin wave in YIG without the hassle of producing auto-oscillations as in [20]. The ECMR, when operating in it’s voltage form, has the potential to lower power consumption level to extremely low level, even after the power dissipation on the electrical side is included. This compares with the above proposed spin wave amplification mechanism that generally require high electric current density to operate [19], [20]. High current density translates to high level of energy waste which completely deviate from the initial motivation of magnonics for being more energy efficient. On the other hand, the relatively low operation bandwidth of an ECMR, which might seems to be a drawback at a first glance, could also turn into an advantage as this lead to “fading memory” effect that is desirable in reservoir computing [25], which itself is an important sub-topic of neuromorphic computing. Therefore, as mentioned in [23], [24], there are motivations

and possibilities to use ECMRs as the building block for magnonic neuromorphic circuitry design (Fig. 1c).

The concept of later so called “chiral magnonic resonator” (CMR) was originally introduced in three dimensional (3D) format in the beginning [26]. Follow up development on this concept includes: Introducing an analytical model [27], extending to non-linear behaviour [28], electrifying using voltage controlled magnetic anisotropy [23] and spin orbit torque [24]. Unfortunately, in order to simplify micromagnetic simulation, all of these follow up development works were done in two dimensional (2D) format with the third dimension being ignored. There comes the question of whether these new developments described in 2D model would still be valid when the third dimension is added. This question is especially legitimate to ask when it comes to the non-linear behaviour described in [28] and [24], where the additional degree of freedom introduced by a new dimension may lead to unexpected complication of the transfer characteristic of the device. There is the necessity to scrutinize results of all of these later development works by reverting back to the original 3D format.

Another major motivation to revert CMRs and ECMRs back to the original 3D format comes from the fact that magnonic circuitry, in analogy to it’s electronic counterpart, is supposed to be designed and operate along a line that can turn left and right on a plane (i.e. in analogy with curved copper wires on a circuit board). This render the micromagnetic models described in [23], [24], [27], [28] unsatisfactory as they consist of a stripe that extend to infinity on the two ends couple to a waveguide in form of a film that also extend to infinity in the same directions. No micromagnetic variation along the third dimension where the stripe and film extend is considered. The fact that the waveguide is represented as a film does not fit the agenda of circuitry design, since for the later case the waveguide has to be something narrow, i.e. a line or more accurately, a conduit (Fig. 1a and b), that can maneuver signal to the left or right on the plane to connect different elements on the same circuit board. At the same time in electronic circuitry design, each electronic device is represented as a lumped element. For example, a resistor is encapsulated in the lumped element model into a single parameter named “resistance”. There is no need to consider the resistor actual dimension, material which the resistor is made of, or actual electron 3D flow pattern during the circuitry design. One would desire a similar lumped element model to exist if to design a neuromorphic circuitry using ECMR as the building block as mentioned earlier. In fact, the introduction of the analytical model in [27] and it’s subsequent development in [23], [24], [28] has achieved this goal. Unfortunately, as aforementioned, these works are developed with the waveguide being represented as a film with no micromagnetic variation allowed in the third dimension (y direction). No variation is allowed either on the second dimension (z direction) due to the small thickness of the film. Effectively the film in these works behave like a single mode waveguide. If we are reverting back to the 3D format, one would requires the resultant magnonic

Fig. 1. (a) Top view of a zigzag shape 80 nm wide and 20 nm thick YIG conduit under micromagnetic simulation. The black arrows represent the relaxed local magnetic moments in the waveguide after saturated with an initial magnetic field that is predominantly in x direction (\mathbf{H}_m) followed by reducing the field strength to zero ($\mathbf{H}_{op} = 0$). (b) Snapshot of the dynamic component of the reduced magnetic moment in z direction after spin waves excited by a transducer at frequency $f_{cw}=3.000$ GHz located at $x = 600$ nm has attained steady state. Clearly spin wave excited at the transducer on the left is capable of propagating through the zigzag region of the conduit at the center and continues their journey to the right. This provide the basis of maneuvering spin wave signal in arbitrary direction on a plane defined solely by the physical shape of the conduit. Regions of spin wave damping are introduced at the two ends of the conduit to absorb arriving spin waves. (c) Illustration of how zigzag shape YIG waveguides combined with ECMRs could form the building block of a neuromorphic computing circuitry. Spin wave (SW) incident from the left into the circuitry undergo modulation by multiple number of ECMR with spin waves intercrossing between different branches of circuitry through directional couplers (DC). The output spin wave exit the system on the right.

conduit to behave also as a single mode waveguide in order for lumped element model to continue to work. In this article, we present using micromagnetic simulation such a design of single mode YIG magnonic conduit with ECMRs coupled to it in 3D manner. A lumped element model of this coupled system is presented and it's predictions are compared side by side with it's micromagnetic model's counterparts. The fair agreement between their predictions suggest that one may be able to design a complicate neuromorphic circuitry (Fig. 1c) relying on the lumped element model alone which is computationally much less demanding and time consuming. The results in this article also vindicate in 3D model the validity of non-linearity [28], amplification [23], and neuron firing behaviour [24] of CMR/ECMR which were previously presented only in a 2D manner.

II. DEVICE DESIGN

A. Device Geometry

The designs of the ECMR device in 3D space are presented in Fig. 2, which is similar to that in 2D [23]. The main differences are: The Ta layer here covers everywhere instead of just under the CoFeB stripe for the convenience of electrical connection to the ground. While the CoFeB stripe still extend to infinity in $\pm y$ directions as in 2D case, the YIG layer and the $\text{MgO}/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Cr}/\text{Au}$ stack above extend only for a width equal w_{wg} in $\pm y$ in the 3D design. Outside this width, the YIG is doped with Ga^+ ion (Ga:YIG) with dosage high enough to reduce local saturation magnetization

Fig. 2. Illustrations of the proposed 3D ECMR device. Quantitative values of the dimensional parameters are given in Table I.

TABLE I
GEOMETRICAL PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED DEVICE

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Thickness of the YIG film	d	20	nm
Width of the YIG waveguide	w_{wg}	80	nm
Vertical separation between the YIG film and the CoFeB stripe	s	20	nm
Width of the CoFeB stripe	w	45	nm
Thickness of the CoFeB stripe	h	2.5	nm

of the YIG to zero [29]. With the magnetic bias field reduced to zero ($\mathbf{H}_{op}=0$) during operation, magnetic moments inside the YIG waveguide will have to point along long axis of the waveguide. Spin waves propagate along the long axis in such a conduit is called “backward volume” spin wave [30]. Because of the short wavelength nature, spin waves excited in this article (at 3.000 GHz) are “exchange dominated” (Fig. 1b). The advantage of such backward volume spin wave over the more popular Damon-Eshbach or Forward volume spin waves [30] lies in the fact that propagation of backward volume spin waves rely on ground state magnetic configuration that does not require a bias magnetic field to maintain (Fig. 1a, $\mathbf{H}_{op}=0$). If the YIG conduit is fabricated to be a curve instead of a straight line, the magnetic moments inside curved conduit will readjust themselves to follow the conduit curvature (Fig. 1a, central zigzag region). When backward volume spin waves reach these curved section of the conduit, they will always propagate towards direction where the local moments are pointing at, i.e. re-adjusting propagating direction defined by the conduit geometry (Fig. 1b). This therefore provides a mean to steer spin wave (i.e. information) on a chip towards arbitrary direction defined only by the fabricated waveguide physical shape, thus form the basis to construct magnonic circuitry on a plane (Fig. 1c).

While initial magnetic field (\mathbf{H}_m) is predominantly in +x direction, it has a small component in the -y direction as well (Fig. 1a and c). When relaxing the system by reducing the field from \mathbf{H}_m to $\mathbf{H}_{op} = 0$, this small component of \mathbf{H}_m in -y direction will ensure all CoFeB stripes to be uniformly

Fig. 3. Dispersion relation of exchange dominated backward volume spin wave along x direction in the YIG waveguide depicted in Fig. 2 for $n_y=0$ (blue curve), and $n_y=1$ (brown curve), where n_y is the mode quantization number along y direction in the waveguide. The horizontal and vertical dotted line depicts the operating frequency ($f_{op} = \omega_{op}/(2\pi) = 3.000$ GHz) and wavenumber ($k_{op}/(2\pi)$) in this article. The corresponding operating wavelength $\lambda_{op} = 216$ nm. Yellow straight line is tangent to the $n_y=0$ dispersion curve at the point of operation.

magnetized towards the -y direction during operation. Due to the chirality nature of CMR/ECMR, magnetic moment in the CoFeB stripes which are located above the YIG waveguide has to point towards -y in order to interact with spin waves inside the waveguide travelling towards +x direction [26]. The CoFeB stripes are designed to extend to the edge of the chip (Fig. 1c). This geometrical continuity of the CoFeB stripe ensure no static surface magnetic bound charge exist due to magnetic moment pointing away from the stripe body other than at the two endings of the stripe at the chip edge. Also the single domain nature of the CoFeB stripe ensure no static magnetic body bound charge exist due to formation of domain wall. Non-existence of static magnetic bound charge prevents static stray magnetic field pointing out of the stripe body anywhere in the chip far away from the edge, in which these static stray field may tune local ECMRs out of targeted resonance.

B. Simulation Results

As mentioned in the introduction, in order for a lumped element model to be easily applicable, the waveguide has to be single mode at the operation frequency. Fig. 3 depicts the dispersion relation of backward volume spin wave inside the waveguide as described in Fig. 2 and Table I. It is apparent the second lowest branch of dispersion would not be excited as long as the excitation frequency is below 4.6 GHz. In this article, we choose the operation frequency to be at 3.000 GHz which guarantee the waveguide to be operating in single mode status. Details of micromagnetic simulation that lead to these dispersion relations results are referred to Appendix A.

The reflection and transmission spectrum of the proposed ECMR device computed by broadband pulse excitation method are presented in Fig. 4. Again, details of micromagnetic simulation that lead to these scattering spectra results are referred to Appendix A. In Fig. 4b, we

Fig. 4. (a) Reflection and (b) Transmission spectrum of spin wave through the proposed ECMR device computed by the broadband pulse excitation method. Blue solid (brown dotted) line correspond to the magnitude (phase) of the reflection or transmission parameter (S_{11} or S_{21}) respectively. Notice that the reflection magnitude in (a) becomes so small for $f < 3.2$ GHz that the $\angle S_{11}$ becomes unable to be determined.

identifies three resonance dips. The dips at $f = 3.929$ and 5.280 GHz are accompanied with weak but visible reflection peaks at the same frequencies in Fig. 4a. On the other hand, in Fig. 4b, there exist a major resonance dip that extends down to $|S_{21}| = 0$ at $f = 3.000$ GHz, while accompanied reflection peak height in Fig. 4a at the same frequency is also next to zero. This resonance at $f = 3.000$ GHz form the basis for us to build an ECMR upon within this article as the YIG waveguide operating at this frequency is single mode as aforementioned. In this article, we disregard the resonances at higher frequencies (i.e. 3.929 and 5.280 GHz) and concentrate our attention at the resonance at 3.000 GHz.

Mode profiles inside the YIG waveguide excited at $f = 3.000$ GHz are presented in Fig. 5. Thanks to the single mode nature of the waveguide at this frequency, the incident spin wave from the left nicely terminates exactly under where the ECMR is located ($x = 2500$ nm) with the spin wave magnitude $|m_y|$ and $|m_z|$ reduced to nearly zero inside the waveguide for region $x > 2500$ nm. This is very important if the ECMR is to be utilized as spin wave attenuator. Suppose the waveguide is not in single mode status, instead of being complete absorbed in the ECMR, spin waves may hop onto the next excitation channel in the waveguide (i.e. $n_y = 1$ mode in Fig. 3) by the help of the ECMR and continue their journey to the right, thus failing the responsibility of the

Fig. 5. Spatially pointwise temporal Fourier transform of z components of the time-dependent magnetization: (a) Magnitude and, (b) Phase of $\mathcal{F}\{m_z(x, y, z, t)\}(f)$ at $f = 3.000$ GHz for $z=10$ nm (middle of the YIG layer) computed using the broadband pulse excitation method. (c) and (d): Same as (a) and (b) except that it is now the y component instead of z .

ECMR to act as an attenuator.

Mode profiles inside the CoFeB stripe excited at $f = 3.000$ GHz are presented in Fig. 6, which suggests the resonance excited is a quasi-uniform mode, asserted from the uniformity of the phase in the center region of the stripe (Fig. 6 b and d, $y \in [80, 200]$ nm), where magnitude of the mode is non-zero (Fig. 6 a and b, $y \in [80, 200]$ nm). The confinement of the uniform mode in this stripe center region ($y \in [80, 200]$ nm) is a direct result of spin wave well produced by the overlaying MgO layer. As depicted in Fig. 2, the MgO layer does not cover everywhere above the CoFeB stripe, but only for a “ECMR” region with width equal w_{wg} along y direction. As the CoFeB-MgO interface provide a source of perpendicular magnetic anisotropy [41], presence of MgO overlayer results in great reduction of dynamic demagnetization field along z direction experienced by CoFeB magnetic moment inside the “ECMR” region. At the same time outside the “ECMR” region, absence of MgO overlayer implies local demagnetization field along z direction remain normal. The reduction of dynamic demagnetization field inside the “ECMR” region results in reduction of local spin precession frequency, thus effectively create a spin wave potential well at the ECMR.

As one may notice, while we have reverted back to 3D in this article as in [26], we have discarded the nano-magnet design of [26] and retain the ECMR in stripe format as in [23]. Unlike nano-magnets, a stripe in single magnetic domain state as mentioned earlier does not produce static magnetic stray field that may detune neighbouring ECMR, which is an advantage. However, retaining stripe geometry produce a new problem: Since ECMRs on the same column are magnetically connected together by the same CoFeB stripe (Fig. 1c), how could we prevent them to interfere with

Fig. 6. Spatially pointwise temporal Fourier transform of z components of the time-dependent magnetization: (a) Magnitude and, (b) Phase of $\mathcal{F}\{m_z(x, y, z, t)\}(f)$ at $f = 3.000$ GHz for $z=41.25$ nm (middle of the CoFeB layer) computed using the broadband pulse excitation method. (c) and (d): Same as (a) and (b) except that it is now the x component instead of z .

each other through spin waves excited and propagate along the stripe? Even though CoFeB has a higher damping factor than YIG, spin waves may still be able to travel far enough from one ECMR to another on the next row in the same column. Here one would appreciate the importance of the spin wave well produced by the overlaying MgO layer as mentioned above, as it confines magnetic oscillations to the local area and prevent ECMRs on the same column to cross talk with each other.

C. Material Parameters

Nice simulation results are often artifacts of unrealistic input material parameters. Therefore there is a need to devote a section to examine the validity of material parameters adopted by the micromagnetic simulation in this article, which is enlisted in Table II. While the values for YIG’s parameters are pretty standard, potential dispute lies with the values for the CoFeB’s. The resonance frequency of the stripe ECMR in [23] is 12.830 GHz. Even we have replaced the dark mode in [23] with the quasi-uniform mode in this article, it would not be enough to bring the resonance frequency down to 3.000 GHz as described above. Such low resonance frequency is essential for the YIG waveguide to operate in single mode as mentioned earlier. It turns out that we were able to reach such a low frequency for the quasi-uniform mode lies with the fact that we have adopted a much lower M_s and A_{ex} value for CoFeB in this article as compared with [23]. In Table III, we have enlisted the M_s , A_{ex} and K_s values of CoFeB reported by a number of experimental papers in the literatures. First of all, material parameters of CoFeB could depend on the exact stoichiometric ratio of Co:Fe:B in the material. The CoFeB parameter in [23] was adopted from [35] in which the $A_{ex}:M_s$ ratio is disproportionately high when compared with the other references in the same table ([33], [36] and [37]). It is unclear that their difference in stoichiometric formula ($\text{Co}_{20}\text{Fe}_{60}\text{B}_{20}$ in [35] vs. $\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}\text{B}_{20}$ in [33], [36] and [37]) might have

TABLE II
MATERIAL PARAMETERS OF THE PROPOSED DEVICE

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Saturation magnetization of YIG	M_s	140×10^3 [31]	Am^{-1}
Exchange constant of YIG	A_{ex}	3.6×10^{-12} [31]	Jm^{-1}
Saturation magnetization of CoFeB	M_s	890×10^3 [33]	Am^{-1}
Exchange constant of CoFeB	A_{ex}	7.9×10^{-12} [33]	Jm^{-1}
Gilbert damping factor of CoFeB	α	0.01 [34]	
Perpendicular anisotropy at CoFeB\MgO interface	K_s	0.990 [32]	mJm^{-2}

contributed to this disagreement. The high $A_{ex}:M_s$ ratio of [35] might have unfairly push the resonance frequency in [23] up to a high value at 12.830 GHz. In this article, the CoFeB M_s and A_{ex} values were adopted from [33] (Table II), which are at the lower end of the range of M_s and A_{ex} enlisted in Table III. The CoFeB material parameters value do not only depends on it's stoichiometric formula, but also on the substrate and seed layer, thickness of the CoFeB film and anneal method [33]. This could account for the inconsistency of CoFeB parameters data in Table III even between those references with identical CoFeB stoichiometric formula. However, in particular the exact amount of Boron contained in CoFeB might have been a dominating factor as the effect of Boron in CoFeB is to dilute magnetic atoms (Co and Fe) in the resultant alloy and increase average separation between them, thus effectively decrease both M_s and A_{ex} [36]. The actual Boron content may not have been correctly reflected in the reported CoFeB stoichiometric formula in some references.

Another focus of dispute would be the CoFeB K_s value under the MgO overlayer. Ideally, one would like to source simulation parameters from a single reference for the sake of consistency. Unfortunately, this is proven to be impossible as those experiment which report value on one particular parameters show no interest in another parameter which might also be essential. The reference we source M_s and A_{ex} in this article ([33]) does not provide value for K_s . The value of K_s used in the article is sourced from [32]. The choice was made mainly because [32] report the same M_s value as [33] (Table III). However, one has to emphasize that this value of K_s we adopted is relatively high, and is essential for the functioning of the ECMR. The high value of K_s contribute to pushing down the ECMR resonance frequency to allow single mode operation as mentioned earlier. Also this high value of K_s increase the precession amplitude of CoFeB in the z direction, which enhance the interaction strength between the ECMR and the waveguide. Without this interaction enhancement, separation between the ECMR and waveguide will have to be reduced to make up the difference which will lead to new problem that would be discussed in section VIII-A. In supplement to the above: Even though Ta has a higher known electrical resistance than Pt, Ta is chosen as the seed layer against Pt in this article because generally Ta seed layer gives

TABLE III
MATERIAL PARAMETERS OF COFeB IN THE LITERATURE

Ref.	Seed	FM/ anneal	Capping	M_s (kAm^{-1})	A_{ex} (pJm^{-1})	K_s (mJm^{-2})
[35]	Ta (10nm)	$\text{Co}_{20}\text{Fe}_{60}$ B_{20} (1.6nm) 280°C	MgO (2nm)	1194	28	1.39
[33]	MgO (001)	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (28nm)		1110	11.1	
[33]	MgO (5nm)	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (28nm)		890	7.9	
[36]	α - Al_2O_3	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (10nm)		1100	13	
[37]	Ta (6nm)	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (17nm)	Ru (0.7nm)	1353	16.2	
[32]	Ta (5nm)	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (1.1nm) 250°C Wet N_2	MgO (2nm)	890		0.99
[38]	Ta (5nm)	$\text{Co}_{20}\text{Fe}_{60}$ B_{20} (2nm)	MgO (1nm)	1257		1.56
[40]	Ta (5nm)	$\text{Co}_{40}\text{Fe}_{40}$ B_{20} (1.0nm)	MgO (2.0nm)	1263		1.28

CoFeB-MgO interface with higher K_s than Pt seed layer [40].

In summary, this article is in no way providing a guaranteed pathway to produce a ECMR device that would function as it is claimed, as the experimental factors controlling the exact value of outcome material parameters are just too complicated to generalize. It would have to come down to each particular experimental group and set up to calibrate and work out their means of material parameters engineering. Instead, the purpose of this article is to provide a set of target material parameter values which fall within a range that is experimentally reasonable to work towards, and the logic behind why these particular parameter values were chosen.

III. LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL

A. Etymology

The main strength of an ECMR circuitry does not lie in neural networks but in reservoir computing because neural network output requires steady state, which takes a long time to attain given the slow time constant of ECMR. On the other hand, output of reservoir computing depends on its transient behaviour, where the memory effect of ECMR slow time constant becomes an advantage. Unlike steady state output, transient behaviour cannot be described by analytical solution but has to be solved numerically. Therefore, the ‘‘analytical model’’ in [23] and [24] is rebranded in this article under a new name: ‘‘lumped element model’’ to reflect this change of objective from obtaining analytical solution to solving problem using numerical method. The ‘‘lumped element’’ nature of the model guarantees a much lower computation burden than the full scale micromagnetic model, but essentially both the lumped element and micromagnetic model solve problem numerically, not analytically.

Fig. 7. Illustration of the lumped element model for the ECMR.

B. Main Theory

The lumped element model in this article is illustrated in Fig. 7. The lower and upper track of waveguide restrict wave to propagate towards the right and left direction, respectively and are described the following wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial \psi_{R(L)}}{\partial t} \pm v \frac{\partial \psi_{R(L)}}{\partial x} + i\Omega_k \psi_{R(L)} = 0 \quad (1)$$

where the \pm symbol takes $+$ and $-$ sign for right going wave ψ_R and left going wave ψ_L respectively. Suppose at $x = x_0^\pm$, $\psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\pm, t) = \psi_0(t)$. Then for any $x > (<)x_0$, solution that satisfies Eq. (1) is given as

$$\psi_{R(L)}(x, t) = \psi_0(t \mp [\frac{x - x_0^\pm}{v}]) e^{\mp i\Omega_k (\frac{x - x_0^\pm}{v})} \quad (2)$$

where the \pm (\mp) symbol takes $+$ ($-$) and $-$ ($+$) sign for right going wave ψ_R and left going wave ψ_L respectively. Dispersion relation of Eq. (1) is given by $\omega = \Omega_k + vk$, represented as a yellow straight line in Fig. 3, with Ω_k and v is fit to be $2\pi \times 0.872$ rad GHz and $0.461 \mu\text{m/ns}$ respectively. On the other hand, the resonator (black dot in the center of Fig. 7) is described by a state variable φ in which it's time dependence obeys the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_{\text{NL}}|\varphi(t)|^2} \frac{\partial \varphi(t)}{\partial t} + i(\frac{\Omega_x + \Omega_z}{2} - i\Gamma_{\text{tot}})\varphi(t) + i(\frac{\Omega_x - \Omega_z}{2})\varphi^*(t) = iI_R + iI_L + iI_D \quad (3)$$

where

$$I_{R(L)} = -\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \right) \Delta_{R(L)}^* \psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\mp, t) - \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} - \sqrt{\epsilon} \right) \Delta_{R(L)} \psi_{R(L)}^*(x_0^\mp, t) \right\} \quad (4)$$

is the waveguide driving force on the resonator, $\epsilon = \sqrt{\Omega_x/\Omega_z}$ is the resonator precession ellipticity. The term $\lambda_{\text{NL}}|\varphi(t)|^2$ in Eq. (3) represents contribution from non-linearity. Unless otherwise stated, λ_{NL} is set to be 0.38 to achieve best agreement with micromagnetic simulation data. The driving term I_D is the driving force from direct dipolar

coupling with adjacent resonator(s), which will be discussed in Section IV-B. The back action of the resonator on the waveguides are described by the follows:

$$\psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\pm, t) = \psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\mp, t) - \frac{i\eta\Delta_{R(L)}}{2v} \times \left\{ \sqrt{\epsilon}[\varphi(t) + \varphi^*(t)] + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}}[\varphi(t) - \varphi^*(t)] \right\} \quad (5)$$

where in Eq. (4) and (5) the \pm (\mp) symbol takes $+$ ($-$) and $-$ ($+$) sign for right going wave ψ_R and left going wave ψ_L respectively. Eq. (3), (4) and (5) looks very complicate because we are working in a frame where the resonator (φ) is allowed to precess with ellipticity while the waveguide ($\psi_{R(L)}$) is restricted to precess with perfect circular polarization. Such an arrangement is necessary since voltage based ECMR relies on modulation of precession ellipticity to perform parametric amplification [23], thus require the resonator in the model to have the degree of freedom to modify it's precession ellipticity. The waveguide precession is kept to be perfectly circular polarized for the model to remain as simple as possible. Suppose in Eq. (3) we ignore non-linearity (set $\lambda_{\text{NL}} = 0$) and direct dipolar coupling to neighbouring resonators ($I_D = 0$) and make the following transformation from φ to ϕ :

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varphi \\ \varphi^* \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/\sqrt{\epsilon} & 1/\sqrt{\epsilon} \\ \sqrt{\epsilon} & -\sqrt{\epsilon} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \phi \\ \phi^* \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

then Eq. (3) and (5) will be reduced into a more familiar form:

$$\frac{\partial \phi(t)}{\partial t} + i\{\Omega_0 - i\Gamma_{\text{tot}}\}\phi(t) = -i\Delta_R^* \psi_R(x_0^-, t) - i\Delta_L^* \psi_L(x_0^+, t) \quad (7)$$

where $\Omega_0 = \sqrt{\Omega_x \Omega_z}$ and

$$\psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\pm, t) = \psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\mp, t) - \frac{i\eta\Delta_{R(L)}}{v} \phi(t) \quad (8)$$

Unlike Eq. (3), the absence of a ϕ^* term in Eq. (7) implies the equation accept perfectly circular polarized solution in form of $\phi(t) = \phi_0 e^{-i\omega t}$. This allows us to proceed with a method of parameters fitting that is slightly modified from the one in [23], which is detailed in Appendix D. The results are the fitted values of six parameters: $\Omega_{x(z)}$ ($= 2\pi f_{x(z)}$), Γ_{tot} , $\tilde{\eta}$ ($= \eta/v$) and $\Delta_{R(L)}$ against K_s , which are displayed in Fig. 8. The natural value of K_s is 0.99 mJm^{-2} (Table II). The fittings in Fig. 8 were done for a range of K_s reachable from this natural value via voltage controlled magnetic anisotropy (VCMA) (see [23]). When the model is run, time varying electric voltage applies to each ECMR modifies it's K_s and thus influence values of the six fitted parameters of the ECMR aforementioned. These six parameters in turns determine the time evolution of the ECMR(s) and the waveguide(s) through Eq. (3) and (5). Obviously, Eq. (2), (3) and (5) form a complete set of equations of motion for the ECMR(s) precession and spin waves in the waveguide(s); Eq. (2) describes how the output from an ECMR is related to

Fig. 8. Fitted lumped element model parameters against K_s at the CoFeB\MgO interface of the ECMR.

the input of another ECMR through the waveguide, Eq. (3) tells us how the waveguide input to an ECMR determines its time evolution, while Eq. (5) describe how the ECMR time evolution in turns feedback as output to the waveguide. In the following sections (Section IV to VII), results from the lumped element model always refer to solving Eq. (2), (3) and (5) numerically through Runge-Kutta (RK4) method, with time step equal to 0.2 ps. The relationship of results from the lumped element model to the micromagnetic simulations are detailed in Appendix C.

The main theory presented above looks neat and self

TABLE IV
PARAMETERS FOR THE PHENOMENOLOGICAL MODEL OF $\angle\Delta_L$ SHIFT

Parameter	Value	Unit
a_1	48	degrees
a_2	0.010	mJm ⁻²
a_3	1.000	mJm ⁻²
a_4	0.002	mJm ⁻²

sufficient. Unfortunately, it has its limitation which mainly manifests when non-linearity and rf modulation of K_s are involved. In order to achieve better agreement between the predictions of lumped element model and micromagnetic simulation, a number of amendments to the main theory are brought in as described in the following subsections.

C. Inclusion of K_s ac pumping term only in $\Omega_{x(z)}$

Suppose the K_s of an ECMR is modulated in form of

$$K_s = K_{s0} + \Delta K_s \sin(\Omega_p t + \phi_p) \quad (9)$$

where the pumping frequency $\Omega_p \sim 2\Omega_0$. K_{s0} could also be time varying but is slow with respect to Ω_0 . The first and second term on the right side of Eq. (9) could be read as the quasi dc term and the ac pumping term respectively. It is proposed that within the six parameters of the lumped element model mentioned in the last section, the ac pumping term influence only $\Omega_{x(z)}$, but not the rest of the parameters. In other words, $\Omega_{x(z)}(t) = \Omega_{x(z)}(K_s)$, where K_s is given by Eq. (9), while $\Gamma_{\text{tot}}(t) = \Gamma_{\text{tot}}(K_{s0})$, $\tilde{\eta}(t) = \tilde{\eta}(K_{s0})$ and $\Delta_{R(L)}(t) = \Delta_{R(L)}(K_{s0})$.

D. $\angle\Delta_L$ dependence on modulation

The operation point of the ECMR is chosen to be around $K_s = 1.000$ mJm⁻², where $|\Delta_L|$ is close to zero (Fig. 8a). The choice was made to minimize reflection to satisfy the general expectation that flow of information in a magnonic circuitry is unidirectional. Unfortunately, when Δ_L is close to this $|\Delta_L|$ minimum point, a fixed $\angle\Delta_L$ value is not sufficient to explain data from micromagnetic simulation. In fact, when near to this $|\Delta_L|$ minimum point, $\angle\Delta_L$ has a linear dependence on K_s ac modulation strength ΔK_s . Such dependence is being described phenomenologically by adding a phase shift as

$$\angle\Delta_L \rightarrow \angle\Delta_L + a_1 \left(\frac{\Delta K_s}{a_2} \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{K_s - a_3}{a_4} \right)^2} \quad (10)$$

where the values of a_1 to a_4 can be found in Table IV.

E. Removal of counter clockwise precessions

The equations of the main theory in Section III-B is designed for precession in the waveguide to be maintained perfectly circular. Unfortunately, during rf modulation of K_s , this perfectness of precession circularity is broken in the model. A tiny but detectable counter-clockwise precession component is being generated which leads to elliptical precession of the

Fig. 9. Illustration of counter-clockwise precession filter in the lumped element model for (a) Left going waveguide and (b) right going waveguide and their corresponding symbols.

state variable in the waveguide. This tiny counter-clockwise component is generally harmless to the model as ECMR in the model interacts only with clockwise precessing wave in the waveguides. As far as ECMRs in the model are concerned, the tiny counter-clockwise component does not affect future evolution of the system. However, since ECMRs does not interact with this counter-clockwise component, the tiny counter-clockwise wave remain unattenuated and could accumulate in the waveguides with time. Also, if one is to measure the transmission or reflection of waves in the waveguide, counter-clockwise wave will alter the outcome readings. In order to remove these counter-clockwise precession, we install counter-clockwise wave filter as depicted in Fig. 9. The associated equations are as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \varphi_{CCW}(t)}{\partial t} - i(\Omega_0 + \Gamma_{CCW})\varphi_{CCW}(t) = -i\Delta_{CCW}^*\psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\mp, t) \quad (11)$$

$$\psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\pm, t) = \psi_{R(L)}(x_0^\mp, t) - \frac{i\eta_{CCW}\Delta_{CCW}\varphi_{CCW}(t)}{v} \quad (12)$$

$$\Gamma_{CCW} = \frac{\eta_{CCW}|\Delta_{CCW}|^2}{v} \quad (13)$$

In practice, we choose $\tilde{\eta}_{CCW} = \eta_{CCW}/v = 1/\omega_{op}$, $\Delta_{CCW} = 0.1\omega_{op}$.

IV. TUNEABLE ATTENUATOR

Depending on the time variation and magnitude of the applied voltage, a ECMR could act as either an attenuator, amplifier or signal generator. Also by placing two ECMRs

in series, one would be able to form a “neuron”. These applications are the building blocks for forming magnonic neuromorphic circuitry. In this and the subsequent sections (Sec. IV to Sec. VII), we are going to investigate them one by one.

A. Single attenuator

One of the basic function of a ECMR is to act as an attenuator with the attenuation continuously tuneable by an applied voltage [23]. Fig. 10 illustrate the micromagnetic simulation of such a single attenuator and it's corresponding representation in a lumped element model. Suppose time variation of the applied voltage is in form of a single rectangular pulse that leads to variation of K_s of the ECMR as shown in Fig. 11(a). The resultant transmission of spin wave in the micromagnetic simulation are shown in Fig. 11(b). As expected, the square pulse modulation of K_s change the device state from maximum attenuation ($t < 20$ ns) to largely unattenuated ($20 \text{ ns} < t < 40$ ns), and back to maximum attenuation ($t > 40$ ns). The settling time at transition between the two attenuation states is roughly 7 ns. As one can see from Fig. 11(c), the lumped element model largely reproduce the transmission pattern of the micromagnetic simulation seen in (b).

As indicated in Table V, to produce the data set presented in Fig. 11, the micromagnetic simulation took 48 minutes while the lumped element model took only 2 minutes. To be fair, the two approaches have been implemented through different software and hardware and they are enlisted in the same table. However this seem to tip the balance further to the side of lumped element model against micromagnetic simulation, as one would expect the GPU card used by the micromagnetic model is more streamlined for arithmetic computation against the CPU used by the lumped element model. Also the micromagnetic simulation is using 90% capacity of the GPU card while the lumped element model is using only 9% of the CPU capacity. It is fair to say that the lumped element model, while producing results that is largely identical to those of the micromagnetic simulation, have greatly reduced the computational burden and the time required.

The prediction of reflected signal from the micromagnetic simulation and the lumped element model are displayed in Fig. 11(d) and (e) respectively, both of them remain next to zero throughout the time span of concern. To satisfies the general expectation of unidirectional flow of information in a magnonic circuitry, the ECMR was design to have reflection minimized, which manifest itselfs in the data mentioned above.

Fig. 12 displays the non-linear behaviour of the scattering coefficient of the single ECMR attenuator. The rise pattern of transmission magnitude ($|S_{21}|$) against increasing incident wave amplitude (m_z) agrees with those in [23], [24] and [28] calculated using a 2D model, while this work is the first time for such non-linear behaviour to be verified under 3D. The

Fig. 10. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of a single ECMR tunable attenuator and (b) its corresponding lumped element representation. The ECMR is biased with V_{DC} so that $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$. Since there is no V_{AC} , therefore $\Delta K_s = 0$.

TABLE V

COMPARISON OF TIME PERFORMANCE OF THE LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL WITH MICROMAGNETIC SIMULATION FOR PRODUCING DATA IN FIG. 11

Attribute	Micromagnetic simulation	Lumped element model
Software	Mumax3	Matlab
Hardware	Nvidia RTX 4060	Intel i5-14600KF
Utilization	~90%	9%
Calculation time	48 minutes	2 minutes

3D nature of this work allows us to visualize variations of the mode profile in the y direction, which were previously ignored. Slices of dynamic component of m_z in the x - y plane retrieved from the YIG waveguide are depicted in Fig. 13 for three different incident wave amplitudes. When the excited spin wave amplitude is small, the ECMR located at $x = 1100 \text{ nm}$ absorbs all the incoming wave and no waves are transmitted to the right side of the waveguide (Fig. 13a). After the excited wave amplitude is increased from $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$ to 0.021, a faint but visible transmitted spin wave on the right side of the waveguide appear (Fig. 13b). This transmitted wave become even stronger when m_z amplitude is further increased to 0.035 (Fig. 13c). The transmitted wave in (b) and (c) remain neat and tidy, with no complications such as wave front fragmentation or hopping to waveguide higher order mode ($n_y > 0$) occurs. This ensure simplified representation of the system by the lumped element model remains valid.

The resultant values of $|S_{11(21)}|$ and $\angle S_{11(21)}$ against m_z (related to ψ_R through Eq. (34)) calculated from Eq. (26) to (29) in Appendix B are shown as solid curves in Fig. 12. The agreement of lumped element model with micromagnetic simulation is excellent both for the scattering parameter magnitude and phase.

B. Double attenuators

So far we have focus our attention on one single ECMR. However, in a magnonic circuitry, ECMR does not work alone but in groups. Immediately the problem of direct crosstalk between ECMR arises due to direct dipolar coupling

Fig. 11. (a) Resultant K_s vs. t of a single ECMR attenuator depicted in Fig. 10 due to variation of applied voltage against time. (b) Micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 10a) incident spin wave $m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $m_{z,\text{scat}}(x_2)$ (brown data) vs. time t . (c) Lumped element model (Fig. 10b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_1)\}$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_2)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t . (d) Micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 10a) incident spin wave $m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (blue data) and reflected signal $m_{z,\text{scat}}(x_1) - m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (brown data) vs. time t . (e) Lumped element model (Fig. 10b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_1)\}$ (blue data) and reflected signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_L(x_1)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t . Both in the micromagnetic simulation and the lumped element model the waves are excited at $f_{cw} = 3.000 \text{ GHz}$ with amplitude $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$.

between these ECMRs. How close can two ECMRs be placed side by side to each other without seriously deviate their behaviours from the case of single ideally isolated ECMR? To answer this question, we in this section investigate the transmission behaviour of two ECMRs placed in series connected by a single YIG waveguide. By varying the distance between the two ECMRs and observe the distortion of the transmission spectrum as compared to a single isolated ECMR, we determine the safe separating distance of ECMRs in a magnonic circuitry where direct dipolar coupling between ECMRs can be largely ignored.

Fig. 12. (a) Reflection and (b) transmission coefficient of the single attenuator depicted in Fig. 10 at $f_{cw} = 3.000$ GHz versus z component incident spin wave amplitude m_z computed by micromagnetic simulation (blue circles and brown triangles) and by lumped element model (blue and brown curves). K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000$ mJm $^{-2}$ and $\Delta K_s = 0$.

Fig. 13. Under the micromagnetic simulation depicted in Fig. 10, the m_z spatial profile (with ground state subtracted) for $z = 10$ nm at $t = 50$ ns in a cw excitation simulation at $f_{cw} = 3.000$ GHz for z component incident wave amplitude (a) $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$, (b) $m_z = 0.021$, and (c) $m_z = 0.035$. The spin wave is excited at the transducer centered at $x = 500$ nm, enclosed by a green dotted line rectangle. The ECMR is centered $x = 1100$ nm above the waveguide (see Table VI and Fig. 32), enclosed by a black dotted line rectangle. K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000$ mJm $^{-2}$ and $\Delta K_s = 0$.

Fig. 14. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of two ECMRs placed side by side with no YIG waveguide connecting them. (b) The corresponding representation in the lumped element model.

Fig. 15. Real and imaginary part of coupling constant $\Delta_{12}(= \Delta_{21})$ in Eq. (14) and Fig. 14b vs. center to center distance (p) between the two ECMRs in Fig. 14a found by comparing with micromagnetic simulation results as detailed in Appendix E.

Suppose in the micromagnetic simulation there are two ECMRs sitting side by side as depicted in Fig. 14a, where their state variable in the lumped element model are defined as φ_1 and φ_2 (Fig. 14b). In analogy to Eq. (4), the I_D terms that enter Eq. (3) which govern time evolution of $\varphi_{1(2)}$ will be given as

$$I_D = -\frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} + \sqrt{\epsilon} \right) \Delta_{12(21)}^* \varphi_{2(1)}(t) - \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} - \sqrt{\epsilon} \right) \Delta_{12(21)} \varphi_{2(1)}^*(t) \right\} \quad (14)$$

where $\Delta_{12(21)}$ is a coupling constant that could be found from micromagnetic simulation as detailed in Appendix E). The resultant values of $\Delta_{12(21)}$ vs. the ECMRs center to center distance (p) are displayed in Fig. 15.

Fig. 16a illustrates the arrangement in the micromagnetic simulation for two ECMR attenuators placed in series. The centers of the two ECMRs are aligned with $x = x_0 \pm p/2$ respectively. The availability of $\Delta_{12(21)}$ vs p in Fig. 15 allows one to calculate evolution of the transmission spectrum

Fig. 16. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of two ECMR attenuators placed in series and (b) the corresponding representation in the lumped element model. The two ECMRs are biased with V_{DC} so that both ECMR have $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$.

against p of the two ECMR attenuators system in a lumped element model (Fig. 16b).

However, before looking at transmission spectrum from the two ECMRs system, we should firstly pay attention to those from a single ECMR in which the results are presented in Fig. 17(a) and (b). Results from both the micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 17a) and lumped element model (Fig. 17b) exhibit a single dip of $|S_{21}|$ at $f = 3 \text{ GHz}$. When the single ECMR is replaced with a double ECMRs in series with $p = 325 \text{ nm}$, the micromagnetic simulation and the lumped element model still predicts a single dip of $|S_{21}|$ but with an apparently much wider dip width (Fig. 17c and d). Not much change is observed when the ECMR center to center distance p is reduced to 215 nm (Fig. 17e and f). When p is further reduced to 160 nm , the single dip of $|S_{21}|$ seen in the previous diagrams splits into two (Fig. 17g and h), indicates onset of direct dipolar coupling between the two ECMRs. The $|S_{21}|$ dip minimum nearly touch zero from (a) to (f), but is lifted to significantly non-zero value in (i) and (j) when p is further decreased to 110 nm . The direct dipolar coupling between ECMRs is so strong in (i) and (j) that it handicap the two ECMRs' function as attenuator.

Here we are in the suitable position to answer the question posted at the beginning of this section: How close could we place two ECMRs side by side while still be able to treat them largely as isolated individual? The single ECMR function as an attenuator by producing a single $|S_{21}|$ dip at resonance frequency (Fig. 17a and b). If two ECMRs in series are working largely independent of each other, one should expect this single $|S_{21}|$ dip feature to be preserved and with dip width doubled when compared to the single ECMR case, which is true for the cases of $p \geq 215 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 17c to f). However the split of the single dip into two for $p = 160 \text{ nm}$ (Fig. 17g and h) and lifting of the dip minimum significantly from zero for $p = 110 \text{ nm}$ represents major deviation from operation of isolated ECMRs. Therefore we can assert that $p \sim \lambda_{op}$ ($\approx 216 \text{ nm}$) represents the minimum distance for ECMRs to be placed against each other in circuitry design

without having direct dipolar coupling between them to strongly modify their behaviour from the case of isolated resonators.

V. PARAMETRIC AMPLIFIER

The ECMR behaves as attenuator if applied with a dc voltage. However, as described in [23], the ECMR could become a parametric amplifier if applied with an ac voltage instead. In this section, we investigate the performance of our 3D version ECMR in this article as a parametric amplifier.

The set up in the micromagnetic simulation and the corresponding lumped element model representation of an ECMR amplifier are depicted in Fig. 18(a) and (b) respectively. The applied voltage is a combination of dc and ac voltage, where the V_{DC} determines K_{s0} in Eq. (9), while V_{AC} determines ΔK_s , Ω_p and ϕ_p in Eq. (9). It is a known fact that the magnitude of the transmitted wave exhibit a 2π periodic behaviour against ϕ_p , with the maximum of transmission magnitude achieved when [23]

$$\phi_p = \phi_{p,\max} = -2\angle\psi_0 + 2\angle\Delta_R - \pi \quad (15)$$

where $\angle\psi_0$ could be found from the micromagnetic simulation using Eq. (45), while $\angle\Delta_R$ is available from Fig. 8b. Under the cw simalon condition described in Table VI and plugging in $K_s = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ in Fig. 8b, one can determine from Eq. (15) that $\phi_{p,\max} = 167.4^\circ$.

Fig. 19 depicts variation of the scattering coefficient of the ECMR amplifier against pumping strength ΔK_s . Such dependence has already been seen previously [23]. What is new here is that a finite reflection is observed (Fig. 19a) in addition to the amplified transmission (Fig. 19b). Gain start to occur in the transmission ($|S_{21}| > 1$) when ΔK_s increase beyond 0.006 mJm^{-2} and grow to nearly six ($|S_{21}| \sim 6$) when ΔK_s approaches 0.010 mJm^{-2} (Fig. 19b). On the other hand, reflection remain small ($|S_{11}| \leq 0.15$) even when ΔK_s approaches 0.010 mJm^{-2} (Fig. 19a). This ensure opeation of the amplifier remain unidirectional and reflected signal does not play any important part in determinating evolution of spin wave in the magnonic circuitry.

The main feature that distinguish this work from that of [23] is that the micromagnetic simulation here is done in 3D. Therefore it is important to show screen capture of the spin wave profile of the waveguide in the x-y plane when the amplifier has achieved amplifying steady state. Fig. 20 presents such data. Spin waves excited from the transducer on the left have their amplitude substantially increased after propagating through the underneath region of the ECMR located at the center, and continue their propagation to the right with the increased amplitude. No abnormality in the amplified spin wave on the right is observed, i.e., no wave front fragmentation or hopping to waveguide higher order mode ($n_y > 0$). Such neat and tidy behaviour of the amplified

Fig. 17. The transmission spectrum of a single ECMR attenuator obtained using broadband pulse excitation from (a) micromagnetic simulation and (b) lumped element model. The rest of the figure (c) to (j) corresponds to transmission spectrum for two ECMR attenuators placed in series as depicted in Fig. 16 with decreasing p . (c), (e), (g) and (i) present results from micromagnetic simulation while (d), (f), (h) and (j) present results from lumped element model. The calculation of transmission spectrum under broadband pulse excitation in the lumped element model are detailed in Appendix B. K_s of the two ECMR attenuators is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ and $\Delta K_s = 0$.

Fig. 18. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of a single ECMR parametric amplifier and (b) its corresponding lumped element representation. The ECMR is biased with V_{DC} so that $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$. On the other hand, the existence of V_{AC} , contribute to a finite ΔK_s which determines the ECMR amplification power.

Fig. 19. (a) Reflection and (b) transmission coefficient of the ECMR amplifier depicted in Fig. 18 with incident wave at $f_{cw} = \omega_{cw}/(2\pi) = 3.000 \text{ GHz}$ and amplitude $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$ versus pumping strength ΔK_s of Eq. (9) computed by micromagnetic simulation (blue circles and brown triangles) and by lumped element model (blue and brown solid curves). K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{cw}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$.

Fig. 20. Under the micromagnetic simulation depicted in Fig. 18a, the m_z spatial profile (with ground state subtracted) for $z = 10 \text{ nm}$ at $t = 50 \text{ ns}$ in a cw excitation simulation with incident wave at $f_{cw} = \omega_{cw}/(2\pi) = 3.000 \text{ GHz}$ and amplitude $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$ for pumping strength $\Delta K_s = 0.009 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ in Eq. (9). The spin wave is excited at the transducer centered at $x = 500 \text{ nm}$, enclosed by a green dotted line rectangle. The ECMR is centered $x = 1100 \text{ nm}$ above the waveguide (see Table VI and Fig. 32), enclosed by a black dotted line rectangle. K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{cw}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$.

Fig. 21. (a) Reflection and (b) transmission coefficient of the single amplifier depicted in Fig. 18 at $f_{cw} = \omega_{cw}/(2\pi) = 3.000 \text{ GHz}$ versus z component incident spin wave amplitude m_z computed by micromagnetic simulation (blue circles and brown triangles) and by lumped element model (blue and brown curves). K_s of the ECMR amplifier is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, $\Delta K_s = 0.009 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{cw}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$.

spin wave ensure the system could be simplified using the lumped element model.

The non-linear behaviours of the ECMR amplifier against increasing incident wave amplitude m_z are displayed in Fig. 21. Same as the case in [23], transmission gain is suppressed substantially as m_z increases (Fig. 21b).

The transient behaviours of the ECMR amplifier against a rectangular pulse spin wave input are presented in Fig. 22.

Fig. 22. (a) Micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 18a) incident spin wave $m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (blue data) and reflected signal $m_{z,\text{scat}}(x_1) - m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (brown data) vs. time t . (b) Micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 18a) incident spin wave $m_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1)$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $m_{z,\text{scat}}(x_2)$ (brown data) vs. time t . (c) Lumped element model (Fig. 18b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}\text{Im}\{\psi_L(x_1)\}$ (blue data) and reflected signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}\text{Im}\{\psi_L(x_1)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t . (d) Lumped element model (Fig. 18b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_1)\}$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_2)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t . Both in the micromagnetic simulation and the lumped element model the waves are excited at $f_{\text{cw}} = \omega_{\text{cw}}/(2\pi) = 3.000$ GHz with amplitude $m_z = 1.4 \times 10^{-4}$. K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000$ mJm $^{-2}$, $\Delta K_s = 0.009$ mJm $^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{\text{cw}}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$.

These time response patterns have already been seen in [23] and [24]. The settling time of the amplified transmission signal here is roughly 50 ns (Fig. 22b and d), which is significantly longer than the settling time of 7 ns in the attenuator case (Fig. 11b and c). The elongation of settling time and the narrowing of bandwidth in amplifier compared to attenuator has already been discussed in details in [23] and [24].

VI. ECMR NEURON

The concept of ECMR neuron has been introduced in [24] using spin orbit torque (SOT) as the pumping mechanism. It is unclear whether the same neuronic transmission effect

Fig. 23. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of a ECMR neuron and (b) its corresponding lumped element representation. The ECMR on the left and right are biased with V_{DC1} and V_{DC2} so that their K_{s0} are at 0.993 and 1.000 mJm $^{-2}$ respectively. On the other hand, a V_{AC} is applied to the left ECMR in addition to V_{DC1} which give rise to a $\Delta K_s = 0.010$ mJm $^{-2}$ with $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{\text{cw}}$. In the lumped element model, the ΔK_s for the amplifier ECMR is slightly brought down to 0.0095 mJm $^{-2}$ to obtain better agreement with the micromagnetic simulation. Also a ccw precession filter is inserted behind the amplifier to absorb any ccw precession generated by the amplifier.

would remain if the SOT pumping is replaced with VCMA parametric pumping. In this article, we present such a result. The micromagnetic simulation arrangement and the corresponding lumped element representation of the ECMR neuron are displayed in Fig. 23(a) and (b) respectively. In the original design [24], the ECMR neuron is formed by placing a SOT ECMR (off resonance pumped) in series with a VCMA ECMR. The first SOT ECMR act as amplifier while the second VCMA ECMR act as attenuator. Here in Fig. 23(a), we retain the same design, but replace the first SOT amplifier with a VCMA amplifier. This amplifier is biased at $K_{s0} = 0.993$ mJm $^{-2}$. The values of f_x and f_z at $K_s = 1.000$ mJm $^{-2}$ in Fig. 8(d) gives a resonance frequency $f_0 = 3.000$ GHz. Setting the K_{s0} at 0.993 mJm $^{-2}$ will raise the f_0 to a value higher than 3.000 GHz. This would match with the off resonance pumping design in [24] given that our operation frequency $f_{\text{op}} = 3.000$ GHz. On the other hand, the second ECMR in Fig. 23 is a normally biased attenuator ECMR with resonance frequency $f_0 = 3.000$ GHz, which is also in agreement with the design in [24]. Together they yield the neuronic transferal characteristics which are displayed in Fig. 24, which has a similar pattern with that in [24]. In Fig 24(b), the $|S_{21}|$ starts with next to zero values for incident wave amplitude $m_z < 0.01$, which corresponds to the neuron dormant state. When m_z exceeds 0.01, $|S_{21}|$ jump to value higher than 1.0 which corresponding to the neuron firing state. As m_z further increase, $|S_{21}|$ gradually drops to lower value implying the neuron has a optimal incident amplitude for maximum output. Further increase in input will counterintuitively gives smaller output amplitude instead of a larger output. On the other hand, reflection $|S_{11}|$ remain low for all input m_z values (Fig 24a).

In order to obtain a full picture of the device performance, one must not pay attention only to the cw transferal characteristic presented in Fig. 24, which are evaluated after

Fig. 24. (a) Reflection and (b) transmission coefficient of the EMCR neuron depicted in Fig. 23 at $f_{cw} = \omega_{cw}/(2\pi) = 3.000$ GHz versus z component incident spin wave amplitude m_z computed by micromagnetic simulation (blue circles and brown triangles) and by lumped element model (blue and brown solid curves). K_s of the EMCR amplifier on the left in the micromagnetic simulation is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 0.993$ mJm $^{-2}$, $\Delta K_s = 0.010$ mJm $^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{cw}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$. For the lumped element model, the ΔK_s is slightly lowered to 0.0095 mJm $^{-2}$ to reach better agreement with the micromagnetic simulation. On the other hand, the EMCR attenuator on the right has $K_{s0} = 1.000$ mJm $^{-2}$ and $\Delta K_s = 0$, both for the micromagnetic simulation and for the lumped element model.

the system attained steady state, but also to the transient behaviour leading to that steady state. Such results are presented in Fig. 25. In Fig. 25(a) to (d), the blue data represent the incident wave to the neuron with increasing amplitude m_z . For $m_z = 0.0021$ (Fig. 25a), the neuron output (brown data) quickly attain a diminished amplitude compared to the input (blue data) before $t = 20$ ns. For $m_z = 0.0115$ (Fig. 25b), the neuron output (brown data) attains a minimum early in the simulation ($t < 20$ ns), but slowly grow afterwards. It is apparent that even at the end of our simulation ($t = 100$ ns), the growing process of the output has not yet end. For $m_z = 0.0131$ (Fig. 25c), the neuron output (brown data) attains a maximum slightly larger than the input (blue data) before $t = 40$ ns, then settle down slightly below this maximum until the end of the simulation. Finally, when m_z is increased to 0.0370 (Fig. 25d), the output attain steady state before $t = 20$ ns similar to the situation in (a).

In order to quantify the transient behaviour of the neuron against incident wave amplitude, we define the settling time

Fig. 25. Lumped element model (Fig. 23b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R((x_0 - \lambda_{op}/2)^-)\}$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R((x_0 + \lambda_{op}/2)^+)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t for incident wave amplitude $m_z =$ (a) 0.0021, (b) 0.0115, (c) 0.0131 and (d) 0.0370. (e) The settling time (t_{settle} defined in Eq. (16)) vs. incident wave amplitude m_z (brown solid curve). The black circles represent the data point corresponding to the time evolution of $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi\}$ presented in (a) to (d),

t_{settle} as the time required for the neuron output to attain steady state. Suppose the output attain steady state at the end of the simulation ($t = t_{\text{end}} = 100$ ns). Write the neuron output as $\psi_{\text{out}}(t) = \sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R((x_0 + \lambda_{op}/2)^+)\}(t)$, then

$$\frac{|\text{mag}\{\psi_{\text{out}}\}(t_{\text{settle}}) - \text{mag}\{\psi_{\text{out}}\}(t_{\text{end}})|}{\text{mag}\{\psi_{\text{out}}\}(t_{\text{end}})} = 0.05 \quad (16)$$

The resultant t_{settle} against incident wave amplitude m_z are displayed in Fig. 25(e). Apparently, t_{settle} remain below 20 ns for most values of m_z , but exhibits a sharp peak at

Fig. 26. (a) The micromagnetic simulation arrangement of an ECMR signal generator and (b) its corresponding lumped element representation. The ECMR is biased with V_{DC} so that $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$. On the other hand, the existence of V_{AC} , contribute to a finite ΔK_s which determines the ECMR emission strength. In the lumped element model, the arrow below the signal generator icon represents the direction of spin wave emissions.

around $m_z = 0.011$ which is where $|S_{21}|$ jumps from low to high state in Fig. 24(b). Therefore suppose the input signal is a rectangular pulse instead of a cw signal, then the pulse duration will also be an important factor in influencing the neuron output signal amplitude, especially if the input pulse amplitude is near to the transition region presented in Fig. 24(b).

VII. SIGNAL GENERATOR

Ref. [24] predicts that when the pumping strength on a SOT ECMR exceed an critical level, the ECMR will be destabilized and auto-oscillates. The oscillate amplitude grows until magnetic moment of the ECMR as a whole flip direction. The major difference when VCMA pumping replace SOT pumping is that in case of VCMA pumping, the auto-oscillation is self-limited. This is due to the fact that SOT pumping is frequency broadband while VCMA pumping pumps at a single frequency ($\Omega_p/2 = \Omega_0 = \omega_{op}$). When oscillation amplitude increase in case of VCMA pumping, nonlinearity lead to further downshift of resonance frequency away from the pumping frequency and stop the pumping process from further increasing the oscillation amplitude. This self-limiting mechanism is absence in case of SOT pumping as the it pumps all frequency at the same time. The fact that VCMA pumping generate sustained oscillations in nano-magnet was utilized to preform electric field excited ferromagnetic resonance measurement [44]. Here in this article the same sustained oscillation could be used to emit spin wave into the coupled YIG waveguide. This utilization is demonstrated in Fig. 27. Because of the asymmetry of magnitude between Δ_R and Δ_L (Fig. 8a and b), emission of spin wave in the waveguide is unidirectional to the right. Such phenomenon was first predicted in [45].

To further understand the spin wave emission phenomenon depicted in Fig. 27, one has to pay attention to the transient behaviour of the system before steady state has been reached. Fig. 28 presents such a study. In both the case of Fig. 28(a),

Fig. 27. Under the micromagnetic simulation depicted in Fig. 26a, the m_z spatial profile (with ground state subtracted) for $z = 10 \text{ nm}$ at $t = 80 \text{ ns}$ in a cw excitation simulation with no incident wave from the transducer (other than the initial seed wave described in the text) for pumping strength $\Delta K_s = 0.020 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ in Eq. (9). The ECMR is centered $x = 1100 \text{ nm}$ above the waveguide (see Table VI and Fig. 32), enclosed by a black dotted line rectangle. K_s of the ECMR attenuator is given by Eq. (9), where $K_{s0} = 1.000 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, $\Omega_p = 2\omega_{cw}$ and $\phi_p = 167.4^\circ$.

(b) and (c), an initial incident wave has been applied. This initial excitation wave is turned off at $t = 5 \text{ ns}$. In Fig. 28(a) where the pumping strength equal $\Delta K_s = 0.010 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$, at the moment when the incident wave is turned off (blue data at $t = 5 \text{ ns}$), a spin wave emission is observed in the transmitted channel (brown data) which the oscillation amplitude exponentially decay with time. On the other hand, when pumping strength is increased to $\Delta K_s = 0.013 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 28b), after the initial excitation wave is turned off, the emitted wave amplitude in the transmitted channel (brown data) grows exponentially instead of decaying. The process of growth in amplitude is not yet finished at the end of the simulation ($t = 80 \text{ ns}$). When pumping strength is further increased to $\Delta K_s = 0.016 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ (Fig. 28c), this growth in transmitted signal (brown data) terminates when the oscillation amplitude reach slightly above 0.03. The signal in the transmitted channel (brown data) continue to oscillate at this fixed amplitude afterwards.

Since emitted spin wave from the ECMR in the transmitted channel decay or grow exponentially with time, it is possible to extract a decay/growth constant $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ assuming that $m_z \sim e^{-\Gamma_{tot,p}t}$ (The letter ‘‘p’’ in $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ stands for ‘‘pumped’’). The resultant $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ versus ΔK_s is displayed in Fig. 29 as blue solid line and blue circles. When there is no pumping ($\Delta K_s = 0$), $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ equals $\Gamma_{tot} (= 0.0217\Omega_0)$ as indicated in Fig. 8c. It is predicted in [23] that when the pumping strength $\delta\Omega_0$ exceeds $2\Gamma_{tot}$, the ECMR will enter auto-oscillation regime. As the relationship between $\Omega_0 (= \sqrt{\Omega_x\Omega_z})$ to K_s is established through Fig. 8d, the critical pumping strength ΔK_s that would lead to auto-oscillation is determined to be 0.0118 mJm^{-2} , which agree pretty well with the point when $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ drop below zero in Fig. 29. After $\Gamma_{tot,p}$ turns negative, the oscillation amplitude of the ECMR will grow until being limited by non-linearity (Fig. 28c). This termination oscillation amplitude is recorded versus pumping strength ΔK_s and is displayed as brown solid line and brown triangles in Fig. 29.

One last word on the subject of ECMR signal generator is that according to Eq. 15, there are two allowed phases $\angle\psi_0$ available for the emitted spin waves to take arbitrarily, in which each of them are 180° away from another. In case of a magnonic circuitry, it is likely that there will be multiple

Fig. 28. Lumped element model (Fig. 26b) incident wave $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_0^-)\}$ (blue data) and transmitted signal $\sqrt{\epsilon_{wg}}\text{Im}\{\psi_R(x_0^+)\}$ (brown data) vs. time t for pumping strength $\Delta K_s =$ (a) 0.010, (b) 0.013 and (c) 0.016 mJm^{-2} . Non-linear parameter λ_{NL} is set to 0.44. In both the case of (a), (b) and (c), a rectangular initial pulse of incident spin wave with frequency at f_{op} , amplitude fixed at $\psi_0 = 1 \times 10^{-5}$ and duration of 5 ns were applied. This rectangular pulse incident wave is only visible in (a) (blue data) but not in (b) and (c) because of the changes in y-axis scale.

Fig. 29. With reference to the left vertical axis, the extracted exponential decay/growth constant ($\Gamma_{tot,p}$) vs. pumping strength ΔK_s from the lumped element model (Fig. 26b) (blue solid line) and micromagnetic simulation (Fig. 26a) (blue circles). In the lumped element model, non-linear parameter λ_{NL} is set to 0.44. On the other hand, with reference to the right vertical axis, amplitude of the terminate emitted spin wave (m_z) in the transmitted channel measured at the end of the simulation ($t = 80$ ns) vs. pumping strength ΔK_s in case of the lumped element model (brown solid line) and micromagnetic simulation (brown triangles).

number of ECMR signal generators located in different part of the circuitry. Even all the signal generators are synchronized by the a global pumping ac voltage, there is still an element of randomness related to this degeneracy of two available phases for each ECMR auto oscillators. One of the solution to address this problem is to use a global microwave field to set these signal generators into motion [45] before switching on the pumping ac voltage. This global microwave field can be as weak as possible and it's purpose is to provide seed oscillations to the generators with well defined phases. The initial kick off global microwave field can be turned off once the pumping ac voltage is in.

VIII. DISCUSSION

A. Device Fabrication

This section is devoted to provide a possible fabrication process for the proposed ECMR device, which is illustrated in Fig. 30. Single crystal YIG film of 20 nm thick is grown on Gadolinium Gallium Garnet (GGG) substrate by molecular beam epitaxy (Fig. 30a) or any other deposition method which could ensure high quality nature of the film in terms of damping properties. The film is then exposed to focused ion beam implantation of Ga^+ (Fig. 30b) with a high enough dosage in which the local magnetic moments of the YIG material in the exposed area are being destroyed [29]. Controlled movement of the focused beam together with proper shuttering ensure a channel region of YIG film is not exposed to the Ga^+ implantation (and therefore the local magnetic moment remain intact). The channel running along x axis (Fig. 30b), which forms the waveguide as described in Fig. 2 is 80 nm wide and should be achievable by the focused ion beam implantation with a writing resolution of 10 nm [29]. Subsequently, $\text{SiO}_2(10\text{nm})\backslash\text{Ta}(10\text{nm})\backslash\text{CoFeB}(2.5\text{nm})\backslash\text{MgO}(2.5\text{nm})$ is being deposited on to the top of the YIG film by rf and dc magnetron sputtering without breaking the vacuum (Fig. 30c). The sample is then subject to annealing under strong bias magnetic field in z direction to introduce a strong magnetic anisotropy at the $\text{CoFeB}\backslash\text{MgO}$ interface. Lithography is then being performed on the top of the MgO layer. Subsequent reactive ion beam etching (RIE) and wet etch would remove the MgO and CoFeB materials which are not covered by the resist, and thus define a $\text{CoFeB}\backslash\text{MgO}$ stripe running along y axis (Fig. 30d). Another round of lithography is then performed. Subsequent thermal evaporation and lift-off will then create the $\text{Cr}\backslash\text{Au}$ top electrode pad (Fig. 30e). Finally, using this top metallic electrode as mask, one can perform another round of RIE and remove the MgO that is not covered under the top electrode (Fig. 30e), thus establish the ECMR device as presented earlier in Fig. 2 (Fig. 30f).

B. Energy Consumption

Here we dedicate a few words regarding energy consumption of the ECMR device proposed in this article. According to [35], an electric field change equal to 0.667

Fig. 30. An exemplary fabrication procedure of the proposed ECMR device.

V/nm leads to a change in the surface anisotropy ΔK_s equal to 0.04 mJm^{-2} . The VCMA amplifier in this article that requires $\Delta K_s = 0.010 \text{ mJm}^{-2}$ to operate would, therefore, require an ac electric field with a peak amplitude that equals 0.167 V/nm . Assume the thickness of the dielectric spacer between the CoFeB layer and the top electrode to be s_2 (Fig. 2). Then, capacitance of the VCMA amplifier is given as $C = \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 w w_{wg} / s_2$, where ϵ_0 is the dielectric constant and ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the spacer. Peak current of the device is then given by $I = \omega C V_0$, where V_0 is the peak applied voltage. Therefore the peak current density is $J = I / w_{wg} / (h + s_1) = \omega / (h + s_1) \times (V_0 / s_2) \times \epsilon_r \epsilon_0 w$. Plugging in $\omega = 2\pi \times 2 \times 3.000 \text{ rad GHz}$, $h + s_1 = 12.5 \text{ nm}$, $V_0 / s_2 = 0.167 \text{ V/nm}$, $\epsilon_r = 10$ and $w = 50 \text{ nm}$, one would find $J = 2.01 \times 10^9 \text{ Am}^{-2}$. The temperature due to joule heating in the Ta layer at this current density level would be neglectable ($\ll 1^\circ\text{C}$)

[24]. Subsequently, the energy for the VCMA amplifier to process a 100 ns spin wave pulse would be $E_{100\text{ns}} = P \Delta t_{\text{sw}}$, where $P = \rho_{\text{Ta}} J^2 w_{wg} w s_1$. Plugging in values: $\rho_{\text{Ta}} = 1900 \text{ } \Omega\text{nm}$ and $s_1 = 10 \text{ nm}$ gives $E_{100\text{ns}} = 2.76 \times 10^{-17} \text{ J}$, which is a very competitive number compared with some other computational technologies [24].

C. Challenges Ahead

It has to be emphasized that despite the optimism so far in this article, there are fundamental issues regarding ECMR magnonics before it could be taken seriously as a contender for neuromorphic computation. One of the main concerns is that there are no experimental data available in the literature regarding spin wave damping in YIG magnonic nanoduits at our proposed wavelength ($\lambda_{\text{op}} = 216 \text{ nm}$). Usually spin wave damping becomes severe when plain YIG film is fabricated into nanoduit, as edge roughness of the nanoduit enhance undesired random spin wave scattering. Ref. [46] excited backward volume spin wave in a YIG magnonic nanoduit that is 44 nm thick and 50 nm wide, which is a dimension comparable to the one in this article (20 nm and 80 nm). Because of the dimension of their microstrip antenna and also limitation of the detection method, the spin wave that is excited and detected has a wavelength equals $2.51 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$ which is much longer than our proposed value. At this wavelength value, they report a spin wave decay length equal $1.8 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, i.e. the spin wave undergo less than one cycle of oscillations before being significantly damped. However, such disappointing behaviour may have been resulted from the fact that the excited wavelength ($2.51 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$) is much longer than the width of the waveguide (50 nm). One would expect such damping phenomenon to be suppressed as the ratio of width to wavelength is increased to our case ($80 \text{ nm} : 216 \text{ nm}$). Unfortunately, no experiment has been conducted yet at such waveguide width and wavelength, due to the technical difficulty of spin wave excitation and detection at these dimension levels.

Another major issue is that there are still some discrepancies between the predictions from the lumped element model and the micromagnetic simulation in some of our results. In Fig. 24, micromagnetic simulation data for $|S_{21}|$ is significantly lower than the lumped element model predictions for $m_z > 0.02$. Such discrepancies decrease when the amplifier-attenuator separation in the neuron (Fig. 23) is increased from λ_{op} to $2\lambda_{\text{op}}$, and vanish when the separation is further increased to $3\lambda_{\text{op}}$ (data not shown), which implies the discrepancies is originated by the direct interaction between the amplifier and the attenuator. Currently, our lumped element model does not reach the necessary numerical accuracy when non-linearity and inter-ECMR direct dipolar coupling are involved at the same time. Major refinement is needed regarding our model, otherwise the model could only be applied to circuitry with large physical separation between ECMRs, where direct dipolar coupling between them are negligible.

Another fundamental issue regarding ECMR magnonics is that there are no reliable read out mechanism available at this moment. The low energy operation of spin wave is its advantage and weakness at the same time. The low energy nature of spin wave implies when converted back into electrical signal, the signal is often too weak to be detected. Traditionally, spin waves are detected by magnetic induction to neighbouring microstrips. These microstrips are usually extremely long (compared to the spin wave wavelength) in order to collect a long wavefront of spin wave to produce enough electrical signal [10], [12], [47], [48]. Surely such scheme is incompatible with our main theme of miniaturization and circuitry operation where the waveguide width (and therefore the wavefront) is shorter than a single wavelength. Another solution is to deposit another magnetic layer with fixed magnetic moment on the top of the MgO below the top Cr\Au electrode in some of our ECMRs to convert them into tunnelling magnetoresistors (detector ECMR). Spin wave in the YIG waveguide induced resonance oscillation of the CoFeB free layer in these converted ECMRs will lead to an ac electrical signal via tunnelling magnetoresistance (TMR) signal, thus indirectly detects spin wave in the YIG waveguide itself. High bandwidth measurement of full magnetization reversal in such free layer has been realized [49]. However, the electrical noise floor in these published data suggests that TMR signal produced by small oscillations of the free layer in our case would be buried under the noise. Surely electrical readout in our ECMR magnonics remains a formidable problem ahead.

D. Thermal Fluctuations

The electrical noise discussed in the last subsection is hinting towards an even greater crisis. So far we have performed all our micromagnetic simulation at temperature $T = 0$ K. In Fig. 31(a), we take advantage of the built-in thermal fluctuation excitation field in MuMax3 [42] and set $T = 300$ K. The resultant m_z data has been averaged over boxes with a length equal $0.5\lambda_{\text{op}}$ in x direction, which is the relevant length scale for the operation of our ECMR circuitry. If one expects the ECMR circuitry in this article to be operating around the firing trigger threshold of the ECMR neuron, i.e. $m_z \sim 0.01$, then one could assert that the signal would be submerged deeply below the thermal spin wave noise (Fig. 31a, $m_z \sim 0.03$ to 0.05). Fig. 31(b) describes how the noise level is downgraded as T is lowered to 0.1 K. Fig. 31(c) summarizes the thermal spin wave noise level against temperature. Apparently, ECMR circuitry in the current form in this article could only work at a comfortable signal to noise level at extremely low temperature ($T < 10$ mK). Unfortunately material parameters used in this article (Table II) are very likely to reshuffle their values at these exotic temperatures [50]. Another route to rescue this crisis would be to increase the non-linear threshold of an ECMR in order to allow operating at a larger spin wave amplitude level above the noise floor at room temperature. This could be done by decreasing the waveguide-resonator separation (s), increasing

Fig. 31. (a) Thermal spin wave $m_{z,\text{th}}$ averaged over a $0.5\lambda_{\text{op}} \times w_{\text{wg}} \times d$ (x,y and z direction) box inside the YIG waveguide centered at $x_{\text{ctr}} = x_1$ (blue data) and $x_{\text{ctr}} = x_2$ (brown data) with temperature $T = 300$ K. (b) Same as in (a) except $T = 0.1$ K. (c) Root mean square of $m_{z,\text{th}}$ over time span of 20 ns against temperature T for the box centered at $x_{\text{ctr}} = x_1$ (blue circles) and $x_{\text{ctr}} = x_2$ (brown squares). The red horizontal dotted line at $m_z = 10^{-2}$ indicates the firing trigger threshold for an ECMR neuron (Fig. 24).

intrinsic damping of the resonator material (α) and increasing pumping strength ΔK_s . Surely, thermal fluctuation remains the most formidable obstacle in miniaturizing magnonics to nanoscale, since as the volume averaged over when making measurement decreases, thermal randomness becomes more prominent.

IX. CONCLUSION

In conclusion we have presented a device design that allows the previous ECMR concept developed in 2D [23], [24] to extend to 3D. The waveguide consists of a magnonic nanoconduit together with the small lateral footprint of the ECMR, allowing complex magnonic circuitry to be designed in a plain provided by a monolith YIG continuous film. The waveguide is single mode at the operation frequency, thus allowing the micromagnetic system to be simplified as an abstract lumped element model. Such simplification allows fast analysis of designed magnonic circuitry without constantly referring back to the time/computational power-consuming micromagnetic simulation. By controlling the applied DC and AC voltage on ECMR, we have demonstrated that the ECMR could be

made to behave as one of the following four applicational devices: Variable attenuator, amplifier, neuron or signal generator. The signal generators acts as spin waves source, while their amplitudes in the circuitry are modulated by variable attenuators and amplifiers. The neurons provide the acute non-linearity usually required by arithmetic or logical operation. It is expected the above four main applicational devices of ECMR form the building block to the emerging ECMR magnonic circuitry. Meanwhile, it is worth to mention that the neuronic behaviour powered by SOT ECMR in [24] is demonstrated to be also feasible with the SOT pumping mechanism replaced with VCMA pumping. However it is also discussed at the end that formidable challenges remain with ECMR magnonics, in particular the thermal noise floor problem and the challenges to raise non-linear threshold of an ECMR to a higher value. ECMR magnonics cannot be taken seriously unless acceptable solution are proposed to meet with these challenges.

APPENDIX A DETAILS OF MICROMAGNETIC SIMULATIONS

Mumax3 [42] micromagnetic package is deployed to implement the broadband pulse excitation simulation and the cw excitation simulation. Cell size is set to be $5 \times 5 \times 2.5$ nm³ in x, y and z directions, respectively. Fig. 32 illustrates the model in 3D. Periodic boundary conditions are applied to the $x = 0$ and $x = x_{\text{total}}$ plane, and to the $y = 0$ and $y = y_{\text{total}}$ plane. No global bias magnetic field is applied during the simulation. The initial magnetic moment in the YIG waveguide and in the CoFeB stripe are oriented towards +x and -y direction, respectively, and the system is relaxed for 50 ns to obtain the ground state. Subsequent dynamic simulation are done with the ground state as the starting magnetic moment configuration. In Fig. 32, the dark purple surface on the top of the CoFeB stripe represents the interface with MgO, where the z direction surface anisotropy K_s is set to $K_{s0} = 1.000$ mJm⁻² unless otherwise stated. At the same time, the light purple surface on the top of CoFeB stripe is not covered by MgO and therefore K_s on these surfaces are set to zero ($K_s = 0$). These surface anisotropy values are converted into volume anisotropy by the relation $K_v = K_s/h$ and applied to the CoFeB magnetic moment unit cells below the surface.

Both the broadband pulse excitation and the cw excitation simulations consist of three stages: The ‘‘scattering stage’’ (Fig. 33(a), abbreviated as ‘‘sct’’), the ‘‘reference stage’’ (Fig. 33(b), abbreviated as ‘‘ref’’) and the ‘‘perfect reflection stage’’ (Fig. 33(c), abbreviated as ‘‘pft’’). To launch spin waves, an excitation field defined as $b_z(x, t)$ which takes the form as described in Table VI is applied in the transducer region (Fig. 32 and 33, red area). The simulation start at $t = 0$ and stop at $t = t_{\text{max}}$. The z components of the magnetic moment dynamics at $x = x_1$ and x_2 are recorded and averaged across the cross section of the YIG waveguide according to Eq. (36) and are labeled as $\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_1, t)$, $\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_2, t)$, $\bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)$,

$\bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_2, t)$, $\bar{m}_{z,\text{pft}}(x_1, t)$, $\bar{m}_{z,\text{pft}}(x_2, t)$ for the case of sct, ref and pft stage. For the case of broadband pulse excitation simulation, these recorded magnetic moments are then undergo subtraction of ground state and smoothing with respect to time near to the truncation at t_{max} :

$$\bar{m}_z(x, t) \rightarrow [\bar{m}_z(x, t) - \bar{m}_z(x, 0)] \frac{1}{2} [1 - \tanh(\frac{t - t_{\text{smth}}}{\Delta t_{\text{smth}}})] \quad (17)$$

where the smoothing time parameters are set to be $t_{\text{smth}} = t_{\text{max}} - 2$ ns and $\Delta t_{\text{smth}} = 1$ ns. The resultant $\bar{m}_z(x, t)$ s lead to definition of transmission and reflection parameters as follow

$$S_{21}(f) = \frac{\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_2, t)\}(f)}{\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_2, t)\}(f)} \quad (18)$$

$$S_{11}(f) = -\frac{\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\}(f)}{\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{pft}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\}(f)} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathcal{F}\{\}(f)$ denotes Fourier transform from time to frequency domain. The software code that implement the broadband pulse excitation simulation will be made downloadable in the future [43].

Regarding the cw excitation simulation, magnitude and phase of the scattering parameters are defined as

$$|S_{21}| = \frac{\text{mag}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_2, t)\}}{\text{mag}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_2, t)\}} \quad (20)$$

$$\angle S_{21} = \text{phase}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_2, t)\} - \text{phase}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_2, t)\} \quad (21)$$

$$|S_{11}| = \frac{\text{mag}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\}}{\text{mag}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{pft}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\}} \quad (22)$$

$$\angle S_{11} = \pi + \text{phase}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{sct}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\} - \text{phase}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{pft}}(x_1, t) - \bar{m}_{z,\text{ref}}(x_1, t)\} \quad (23)$$

where $\text{mag}\{\}$ and $\text{phase}\{\}$ denote the resultant amplitude and phase values of a temporal sinusoidal fit to the magnetic moment time dependence after the system has reach steady state.

To calculate the n_y -th branch dispersion relation in the YIG waveguide, an excitation field given by

$$b_z(x, t) = b_{\text{tr}} \frac{\sin(\omega_c(t - t_0))}{\omega_c(t - t_0)} \frac{\sin(k_c(x - x_0))}{k_c(x - x_0)} \times \text{sgn}\{\cos[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_y}(y - (\frac{y_{\text{total}} - w_{\text{wg}}}{2}))]\} \quad (24)$$

is applied to the entire waveguide in Fig. 33b, where $\lambda_y = 2w_{\text{wg}}/n_y$. Dispersion relation (f vs k) is then obtained from the maxima of $|M_z(f, k)|$, where

$$M_z(f, k) = \mathcal{F}\{\mathcal{F}\{m_z(x, y_{\text{line}}, z_{\text{line}}, t)\}(f)\}(k) \quad (25)$$

Fig. 32. 3D illustration of the micromagnetic model.

Fig. 33. 2D illustration of the micromagnetic model, which depicts the three stages (“sct”, “ref” and “pft”) in either the broadband pulse excitation or cw excitation simulation. The “sct” and “ref” stage share the same damping factor (α) profile against x in the YIG waveguide, but with the CoFeB resonator removed in the “ref” stage. In the “pft” stage, the CoFeB resonator is also absent and α is raised to 100 for the right half of the waveguide, creating a wall for perfect spin wave reflection at the waveguide center.

where m_z is the resultant z component magnetic moment dynamics of the YIG waveguide as a function of position and time. Also,

$$y_{\text{line}} = \begin{cases} y_{\text{total}}/2 & \text{for } n_y \text{ is even} \\ y_{\text{total}}/2 - \lambda_y/4 & \text{for } n_y \text{ is odd} \end{cases}$$

and $z_{\text{line}} = d/2$. Also, $\mathcal{F}\{f\}$ and $\mathcal{F}\{k\}$ denote Fourier transform from t to f and from x to k .

APPENDIX B

DETAILS OF LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL CALCULATIONS

Suppose in the lumped element model of Fig. 34, the waveguide is feed with an incident wave $\psi_R(x_1^-, t) = \psi_0 e^{-i\omega t}$, then the magnitude and phase of S_{11} and S_{21} under this cw excitation are then defined as

TABLE VI
PARAMETERS OF THE MICROMAGNETIC SIMULATION MODEL

Parameter	Broadband pulse excitation model	cw excitation model
x_{total}	5000 nm	2200 nm
y_{total}	280 nm	280 nm
x_0	2500 nm	1100 nm
x_1	2100 nm	700 nm
x_2	2900 nm	1500 nm
x_3	1000 nm	400 nm
x_4	4000 nm	1800 nm
x_{tdr}	1500 nm	500 nm
w_{tdr}	1000 nm	216 nm ($= \lambda_{\text{cw}} = \lambda_{\text{op}}$)
α_{wg}	0	2×10^{-4}
α_{dmp}	0.2	0.2
$b_z(x, t)$	$b_{\text{rf}} \frac{\sin(\omega_c(t-t_0))}{\omega_c(t-t_0)} \frac{\sin(k_c(x-x_{\text{tdr}}))}{k_c(x-x_{\text{tdr}})}$	$b_{\text{rf}} \sin(2\pi f_{\text{cw}} t) \cos[\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_{\text{cw}}}(x-x_{\text{tdr}})]$
b_{rf}	1 mT	0.01 mT
ω_c	$2\pi f_c$	
k_c	$2\pi/\lambda_c$	
t_0	1 ns	
f_c	20 GHz	
λ_c	50 nm	
f_{cw}		3.000 GHz ($= f_{\text{op}}$)
t_{max}	20 ns	50 ns

Fig. 34. Illustration of the set up in the lumped element model to calculate the scattering parameters. “DUT” stands for “Device Under Test”.

$$|S_{11}| = \frac{\text{mag}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{L,\text{sct}}(x_1^-, t)\}\}}{\text{mag}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\}} \quad (26)$$

$$\angle S_{11} = \text{phase}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{L,\text{sct}}(x_1^-, t)\}\} - \text{phase}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\} \quad (27)$$

$$|S_{21}| = \frac{\text{mag}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{sct}}(x_2^+, t)\}\}}{\text{mag}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\}} \quad (28)$$

$$\angle S_{21} = \text{phase}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{sct}}(x_2^+, t)\}\} - \text{phase}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\} \quad (29)$$

where $\text{mag}\{\}$ and $\text{phase}\{\}$ denote the resultant amplitude and phase values of a temporal sinusoidal fit to the $\psi(t)$ after the system has reach steady state. Here we have assumed x_1 and x_2 are given as in the micromagnetic simulation in Table VI. Suppose the DUT in Fig. 34 consist of a single or a number of ECMRs connected in series, to simplify calculations, x_1 and x_2 are replaced by the location of the first and last ECMR. The resultant values of S_{11} and S_{21}

should remain the same as long as $(x_1 + x_2)/2 = x_0$ remain true.

To calculate S_{11} and S_{21} in case of a broadband pulse excitation, the waveguide is feed with an incident wave given as

$$\psi_R(x_1^-, t) = \frac{\psi_0}{i(t - t_0)} (1 - e^{-i\omega_c(t-t_0)}) \quad (30)$$

then the scattering parameters are defined as

$$S_{21}(f) = \frac{\mathcal{F}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{sct}}(x_2^+, t)\}\}(f)}{\mathcal{F}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\}(f)} \quad (31)$$

$$S_{11}(f) = \frac{\mathcal{F}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{L,\text{sct}}(x_1^-, t)\}\}(f)}{\mathcal{F}\{\text{Im}\{\psi_{R,\text{ref}}(x_2^-, t)\}\}(f)} \quad (32)$$

APPENDIX C

RELATING LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL TO MICROMAGNETIC SIMULATION

In order to compare predictions of the lumped element model with the micromagnetic model, the follow correspondences (\leftrightarrow) are established based on the coordinate system in Fig. 32:

$$\begin{cases} \bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}(t) \leftrightarrow -\text{Re}\{\varphi(t)\} = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} \text{Re}\{\phi(t)\} \\ \bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}(t) \leftrightarrow \text{Im}\{\varphi(t)\} = \sqrt{\epsilon} \text{Im}\{\phi(t)\} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} \bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}(x, t) \leftrightarrow -(1/\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}) \text{Re}\{\psi_R(x, t) + \psi_L(x, t)\} \\ \bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}(x, t) \leftrightarrow \sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}} \text{Im}\{\psi_R(x, t) + \psi_L(x, t)\} \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

where

$$\bar{m}_{\sigma,\text{res}}(t) = \frac{1}{ww_{\text{wg}}h} \int_{(x_{\text{total}}-w)/2}^{(x_{\text{total}}+w)/2} \int_{(y_{\text{total}}-w_{\text{wg}})/2}^{(y_{\text{total}}+w_{\text{wg}})/2} \int_{z_{\text{total}}-h}^{z_{\text{total}}} m_{\sigma}(x, y, z, t) dz dy dx \text{ for } \sigma = x, z \quad (35)$$

and

$$\bar{m}_{\sigma,\text{wg}}(x, t) = \frac{1}{w_{\text{wg}}d} \int_{(y_{\text{total}}-w_{\text{wg}})/2}^{(y_{\text{total}}+w_{\text{wg}})/2} \int_0^d m_{\sigma}(x, y, z, t) dz dy \text{ for } \sigma = y, z \quad (36)$$

$m_{\sigma}(x, y, z, t)$ for $\sigma = x, y, z$ is the *normalized* local magnetic moment vector in the micromagnetic simulation. The bar sign above $\bar{m}_{\sigma,\text{res}}$ and $\bar{m}_{\sigma,\text{wg}}$ represent averaging over the resonator (res) volume region or waveguide (wg) cross section. ϵ_{wg} is the precession ellipticity of moments in the waveguide and could be obtained in Eq. (43) and (46), which is determined to be 0.675 at the 3.000 GHz operation point in Fig. 3.

Regarding the resonator in a cw excitation simulation, after the system attain steady state, ϕ in Eq. (33) bares solution in

form of $\phi = \phi_0 e^{-i\omega t} = |\phi_0| e^{i(-\omega t + \angle\phi_0)}$. Then one would obtain the relationships:

$$\epsilon = \frac{|\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}|}{|\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}|} \quad (37)$$

$$|\phi_0| = \sqrt{\epsilon} |\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} |\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}| \quad (38)$$

$$\angle\phi_0 = -\pi/2 - \angle\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}} = \pi - \angle\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}} \quad (39)$$

where the $|\bar{m}|$ and $\angle\bar{m}$ sign denote resultant amplitude and phase values of a temporal sinusoidal fit to the averaged magnetic moment time dependence $\bar{m}(t)$.

In case of broadband pulse excitation simulation, the corresponding relationship between lump element model and the simulation becomes

$$\epsilon = \frac{|\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}\}(\omega)|}{|\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}\}(\omega)|} \quad (40)$$

$$|\phi_0| = 2\sqrt{\epsilon} |\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}\}(\omega)| = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\epsilon}} |\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}\}(\omega)| \quad (41)$$

$$\angle\phi_0 = \pi - \angle\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{x,\text{res}}\}(\omega) = \pi/2 - \angle\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{res}}\}(\omega) \quad (42)$$

Regarding the waveguide in a cw excitation simulation, suppose after the system attain steady state, ψ_R and ψ_L in Eq. (34) bares solution in form of $\psi_R = \psi_0 e^{i(kx - \omega t)} = |\psi_0| e^{i(kx - \omega t + \angle\psi_0)}$ and $\psi_L = 0$. Then one would obtain the relationship:

$$\epsilon_{\text{wg}} = \frac{|\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}|}{|\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}|} \quad (43)$$

$$|\psi_0| = \sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}} |\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}| = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}} |\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}| \quad (44)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \angle\psi_0 &= -\pi/2 - kx - \angle\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}} \\ &= \pi - kx - \angle\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}} \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

where the $|\bar{m}|$ and $\angle\bar{m}$ sign denote resultant amplitude and phase values of a temporal sinusoidal fit to the averaged magnetic moment time dependence $\bar{m}(t)$.

In case of broadband pulse excitation simulation, the corresponding relationship between lump element model and the simulation becomes

$$\epsilon_{\text{wg}} = \frac{|\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}\}(\omega)|}{|\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}\}(\omega)|} \quad (46)$$

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_0| &= 2\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}} |\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}\}(\omega)| \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{wg}}}} |\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}\}(\omega)| \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\angle\psi_0 &= \pi - kx - \angle\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{y,\text{wg}}\}(\omega) \\ &= \pi/2 - kx - \angle\mathcal{F}\{\bar{m}_{z,\text{wg}}\}(\omega)\end{aligned}\quad (48)$$

APPENDIX D

LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL PARAMETERS FITTING

This section is aiming at explaining the methodology to obtain the six parameters ($\Omega_{x(z)}$, Γ_{tot} , $\tilde{\eta}$ and $\Delta_{R(L)}$) of an ECMR in the lumped element model of Section III. Firstly, substitute the solutions.

$$\begin{cases} \psi_R(x_0^-, t) = \psi_0 e^{-i\omega t} \\ \psi_R(x_0^+, t) = \tau_R \psi_0 e^{-i\omega t} \\ \psi_L(x_0^+, t) = 0 \\ \psi_L(x_0^-, t) = r_R \psi_0 e^{-i\omega t} \\ \phi(t) = \phi_0 e^{-i\omega t} \end{cases}\quad (49)$$

into Eq. (7) and (8), one would obtain:

$$\phi_0(\omega) = \frac{\Delta_R^* \psi_0}{\omega - \Omega_0 + i\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}\quad (50)$$

$$\tau_R(\omega) = 1 - \frac{i2\Gamma_R}{\omega - \Omega_0 + i\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}\quad (51)$$

$$r_R(\omega) = \frac{ir_{R0}\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}{\omega - \Omega_0 + i\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}\quad (52)$$

where

$$\Gamma_R = \frac{\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}{2}(1 - \tau_{R0}) = \frac{\tilde{\eta}|\Delta_R|^2}{2}\quad (53)$$

and

$$r_{R0} = -\frac{\tilde{\eta}\Delta_L\Delta_R^*}{\Gamma_{\text{tot}}}\quad (54)$$

Thus the parameters are extracted according to the following procedures:

- 1) Perform the broadband pulse excitation simulation. The resultant $S_{21}(\omega)$ obtained from Eq. (18) is related to the $\tau_R(\omega)$ in Eq. (51) according to the relation $S_{21}(\omega) = [\tau_R(\omega)]^*$ (see [23]). This allow us to find the value of Ω_0 , Γ_{tot} and Γ_R by best fitting.
- 2) Calculate the resonator precession ellipticity ϵ according to Eq. (40). Then Ω_x and Ω_z is given by $\Omega_x = \epsilon\Omega_0$ and $\Omega_z = \Omega_0/\epsilon$ accordingly.
- 3) By setting $\omega = \Omega_0$ in Eq. (50), after some rearrangement, one would obtain $\Delta_R = -i\Gamma_{\text{tot}}\phi_0^*/\psi_0^*$. The value of ϕ_0 and ψ_0 could be obtained through Eq. (41), (42), (47) and (48).

- 4) The value of $\tilde{\eta}$ could then be obtained by rearranging Eq. (53): $\tilde{\eta} = 2\Gamma_R/|\Delta_R|^2$.
- 5) In the broadband pulse excitation simulation, $S_{11}(\omega)$ could be obtained from Eq. (19), which is related to $r_R(\omega)$ in Eq. (52) through $S_{11}(\omega) = [r_R(\omega)]^*$ (see [23]). Best fitting between the two leads to the value of r_{R0} .
- 6) The value of Δ_L could finally be founded by rearranging Eq. (54): $\Delta_L = -\Gamma_{\text{tot}}r_{R0}/(\tilde{\eta}\Delta_R^*)$.

APPENDIX E

EXTRACTION OF DIRECT DIPOLAR COUPLING CONSTANT $\Delta_{12(21)}$ IN THE LUMPED ELEMENT MODEL

With referencing to Eq. (7), the rectified state variable ϕ of the two ECMRs as depicted in Fig. 14 where no waveguide exist but are coupled directly to each other by dipolar coupling, and are driven separately by two driving forces ($I_{1(2)}$), should obey time evolutionary equations given as

$$\frac{\partial\phi_{1(2)}}{\partial t} + i(\Omega_0 - i\Gamma_0)\phi_{1(2)} = iI_{1(2)} - i\Delta_{12(21)}\phi_{2(1)}\quad (55)$$

where $\Gamma_0 = \alpha\Omega_0$ as described in [23] and α is the Gilbert damping factor of CoFeB given in Table II. Plugging in solutions to Eq. (55) in form of $\phi_{1(2)} = \phi_{1(2)0}e^{-i\omega t}$ and $I_{1(2)} = I_{1(2)0}e^{-i\omega t}$, one would find

$$\begin{bmatrix} \phi_{10} \\ \phi_{20} \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{(-\delta\omega - i\Gamma_0)^2 - \Delta_{12}\Delta_{21}} \times \begin{bmatrix} (-\delta\omega - i\Gamma_0) & -\Delta_{12} \\ -\Delta_{21} & (-\delta\omega - i\Gamma_0) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_{10} \\ I_{20} \end{bmatrix}\quad (56)$$

where $\delta\omega = \omega - \Omega_0$. By setting $\delta\omega = 0$ and $I_{20} = 0$ in Eq. (56), one would obtain $\Delta_{21} = i\Gamma_0\phi_{20}/\phi_{10}$. Similarly, by setting $\delta\omega = 0$ and $I_{10} = 0$ in Eq. (56), one would obtain $\Delta_{12} = i\Gamma_0\phi_{10}/\phi_{20}$. One should notice that ϕ_{10} and ϕ_{20} are related to their counterparts in a cw excited micromagnetic simulation through Eq. (38) and (39), thus lead us to find the values of $\Delta_{12(21)}$ from the corresponding micromagnetic simulation depicted in Fig. 14.

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